

WOMENS SECURITY GADGET

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Abstract— Purpose of the project is to provide security for woman. In case of emergency situations woman will press an emergency button which will activates the GPS for location tracking and a SMS is sent to Emergency contact number. When the person is trying to harass or abuse a woman he will get shock by the device and the woman will get some time to rescue so she can save herself , simultaneously screaming alarm will get turn ON. When screaming alarm will turn ON people from the surrounding will get gathered to save woman.

Keywords—Women Safety, GPS, GSM, Arduino.

I. INTRODUCTION

The project on "Womens Security System" is proposed to minimize the risk of accidents and will reduce the rate of atrocities. This system is composed of a Arduino- Promini and interface with mobile through Bluetooth module. This is an inexpensive device which reduces the problem associated with accident notification. This application offers a helping hand with the help of GPS based location tracing. At the time of emergency, there may not be any possibility to attempt phone calls or to send messages manually then this application will be very helpful for persons who are at difficulty.

When the device is thrown with high pulse rate, using pulse rate sensor, it will start functioning i.e. it will send location to the police and distress message to the registered mobile number through a GSM module. By simply press of a switch will also send location as well as distress message, via the mobile phone to the police control room and to the other registered mobile numbers, via GSM module.

When the person is trying to harass or abuse a woman he will get shock by the device and the woman will get some time to rescue so she can save herself , simultaneously screaming alarm will get turn ON. When screaming alarm will turn ON people from the surrounding will get gathered to save woman.

II. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 and Figure 2 represents the methodology used in our paper. The device can be activated by just pressing the emergency button once. The location is located using GPS module. With the help of Bluetooth model will connect device with mobile phone, location

is traced and SMS will send to the Emergency contact number. When the person is trying to harass or abuse a woman he will get shock by the device and the woman will get some time to rescue so she can save herself, simultaneously screaming alarm will get turn ON.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

When the device is thrown with high pulse rate, using pulse rate sensor, it will start functioning i.e. it will send location to the police and distress message to the registered mobile number through a GSM module. By simply press of a switch will also send location as well as distress message, via the mobile phone by using Bluetooth connectivity to the police control room and to the other registered mobile numbers, via GSM module. When the person is trying to harass or abuse a woman he will get shock by the device and the woman will get some time to rescue so she can save herself, simultaneously screaming alarm will get turn ON. When screaming alarm will turn ON people from the surrounding will get gathered to save woman.

IV. BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure 1: Block Diagram of Security Gadget

Figure 2: Block Diagram of Bluetooth Application

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to take this opportunity to express our respect and deep gratitude to our guide Prof.Dr.R.P.Labade, for giving us all necessary guidance required, for this project, apart for being constant source of inspiration and motivation. It was our privilege to have worked under him. We are thankful to

H.O.D. Prof.Dr.R.P.Labade & Principal Dr. M.A.Venkatesh for the regular guidance, co-operation, encouragement and kind help. We are highly obligated to our entire friends, whose contribution intellectually and materially in the words and deeds for preparation of this Seminar report. We are also thankful to all our teaching and non-teaching staff for their enormous support.

VI. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the system helps to supports the gender equality by providing safe environment to women in the society and allows them to work till late nights. Anyone before doing any crime against the women will be deterred and it help reducing the crime rate against the women. It is a low cost system which can store the data of the members in the particular locality and provides immediate alert in case of crime against women. So compact in itself that provide advantage of personal security system. It is certainly a short term and preventive solution. This project is a multipronged strategy with the participation of multi stake holders of society

VII. REFERENCES

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